

Using Quizizz as an Alternative Medium in Applying the Picture and Picture Type Cooperative Learning Model in English Subject to Increase Vocabulary Mastery for Primary School Students

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ARTICLE INFORMATION	ABSTRACT
<p>Article History: Received May 2024 Revised June 2024 Accepted June 2024</p> <p>Keywords: Picture and Picture Type Cooperative Learning Model, Quizizz, English Subject, Vocabulary Mastery, Primary Students.</p> <p>*Corresponding Author: adilafebrianti22@upi.edu</p> <p>DOI:</p>	<p>The mastery of English vocabulary of VC class students at UPTD SDN 1 Citalang is still in the low category. This can be seen based on the data from the pre-test results which show the overall average score of students which is only ≥ 40. The efforts that can be made by researchers to solve these problems are by applying the Picture and Picture model assisted by Quizizz. The objectives of this study are: 1) Knowing the ability of English vocabulary mastery of students in grade V elementary school before using the Picture and Picture model assisted by Quizizz. 2) Knowing the ability of English vocabulary mastery of students in grade V elementary school after using the Picture and Picture model assisted by Quizizz. 3) To find out the effect of Picture and Picture model assisted by Quizizz on students' English vocabulary mastery ability in grade V elementary school. Picture and Picture learning model is a cooperative learning model that uses picture media. The Quizizz application functions as a medium to display images so that learning can adapt to digitalization. The research method used is pre-experiment. Based on the results of the study, the average score of mastery of English vocabulary obtained through the post-test increased to ≤ 75. Based on these results, it can be concluded that the Quizizz-based Picture and Picture learning model can improve the mastery of English vocabulary of students in class VC UPTD SDN 1 Citalang.</p>

INTRODUCTION

English learning activities in Indonesia are still not optimal. This is evidenced by data obtained from the English First (EF) English Proficiency Index in 2023, which states that Indonesia is still in 79th place in the low category. EF EPI said that one of the main factors that can cause a country's low English proficiency is the lack of vocabulary mastery.

As we know based on the facts on the ground, English has now become the main capital for a person. As a benchmark for a person's ability, it becomes the main point that is assessed when entering the job market. Because English is an international language, which is the second language that must be learned after the national language. This is also supported by the Ministry of Education, culture, research, and Technology, which has launched the Merdeka curriculum (Oktavia et al., 2023).

In its implementation, the Merdeka curriculum provides opportunities for every educational institution at all levels to carry out English learning activities. In other words, every educational institution in Indonesia is asked to carry out English learning activities as much as possible. By giving equal rights to all students, it is a shared responsibility to optimize the English learning activities carried out.

In this era of technological advancement, we should begin to adapt to the increasingly sophisticated digital transformation. One of them is in the field of education, there are many alternative media for carrying out learning activities that can help optimize the learning

outcomes of students. Adapting to technological advances does not mean eliminating everything that is conventional. But instead, we transform conventional things into digitalization in order to continue to adapt to the latest technology. There are many options that teachers can use to support the digital learning process.

The more technology develops, the more media and other applications that can be used when the learning process takes place. The impact felt from the use of digital-based media is to increase student learning motivation, improve learning quality, familiarize students to adapt to technology, and the most expected is to improve student learning outcomes. Based on the positive impacts of using digital-based learning media, the researcher is interested in knowing how the impact is felt from cooperative learning activities of the picture and picture type which were originally conventionally based, now transformed with a little adaptation using technological assistance so that they become digital-based at UPTD SDN 1 Citalang.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Spencer Kagan first launched the picture-and-picture cooperative learning model in 1989. Kagan argued that cooperative learning can be based on intermediary media that are effective for children, one of which is picture media. According to him, pictures used in learning media provide opportunities for students to obtain more information by describing the picture according to their own opinions.

In its implementation, the picture-and-picture cooperative learning model provides opportunities for students to work together in teams. This is supported by Johnson, who revealed in 2015 that cooperative learning that involves the ability to work together in a team of students can make students more active.

The picture-and-picture type cooperative learning model makes students freer to express their opinions and trains students to be able to work together in teams. The picture media presented in the cooperative learning model of picture and picture type makes students become more imaginative and increases the creativity of students. Because students no longer listen to learning passively, but students are also given the opportunity to participate in learning more actively (Cameron, L. 2001).

The picture and picture type cooperative learning model implemented by students at elementary school age is one of the implementations of the EYL (English for young learners) principle which states that students at elementary school age tend to be imaginative and creative. So that teachers need to provide the best container so that students can channel their learning style characteristics with the right learning method (Ratri, Lailiyah, et al, 2018).

Digital-based learning activities provide many significant benefits. Digital-based learning can be implemented if educational institutions have started using ICT (information communication technology) as a basis for carrying out daily learning activities (Udangmo, 2014). The Quizizz application used as media in this learning activity was made by Deepak Hox Cheernaath from the Indian state company in 2015. The application offers various features that can support the picture-and-picture cooperative learning process.

METHOD

Type of Research

This research was conducted with a pre-experiment method of one group design pre-post test with a sampling data collection technique in the form of non-probability sampling of 5C class students at UPTD SDN 1 Citalang, Purwakarta Regency. Pre-experiment research is an effort to collect various data in predetermined units in order to achieve a specific goal. This research was carried out by collaborating between researchers and students, namely by conducting treatment

or giving treatment in the form of a cooperative learning model of the picture and picture type assisted by the Quizizz application.

Research Time and Location

This research was conducted in the even semester of the 2023/2024 school year at UPTD SDN 1 Citalang, located in Karang Sari Village, Citalang, Purwakarta Regency.

Research Subject

A total of 27 students in class 5C were involved in this study. With 13 male students and 14 female students.

Research Schedule

The research was conducted for 3 days. With details of 1 day for pre-test implementation, 1 day for treatment, and 1 day for post-test implementation.

Data Collection and Analysis Techniques

The data collection technique used is observation and written tests that have been prepared based on indicators of mastery of English vocabulary. Thornbury (2002) and Brewster (2004) suggest that the indicators of English vocabulary mastery are form or vocabulary writing, word meaning or meaning/translation of vocabulary, and usage or using vocabulary.

The observation used in this research aims to ensure that the implementation of the cooperative learning model of picture and picture type is carried out as it should be, in accordance with the implementation steps. The objects observed during this observation process were teachers and students.

The written test used was a test with 5 multiple-choice questions and 3 description questions. Overall, the 8 questions contained all the indicators of English vocabulary mastery that have been formulated previously.

The assessment scale used in this study is a research scale that refers to the assessment and learning guidebook prepared by the Ministry of Education, Culture, Research and Technology of the Republic of Indonesia in 2022.

The assessment stage is carried out objectively by calculating the number of scores obtained by students divided by the total number of questions and then multiplied by a perfect score of 100.

RESULT AND DISCUSSION

This research was carried out by conducting initial activities, such as pre-tests. These pre-tests aim to determine the extent of students' abilities before they are given treatment or treatment. After they are given treatment or treatment, post-test activities are carried out to determine the level of success of the treatment or treatment that has been carried out.

Pre-test	Post-test
39,3	76,3

Based on the results of the data above, the average score of students before the application of the Quizizz-based picture and picture type cooperative learning model was only > 40. The average score has increased after the application of the Quizizz-based picture and picture type cooperative learning model with a score of < 75.

Observation reports or observations to researchers and to students show that the Quizizz-based picture and picture type cooperative learning model runs as it should by following each implementation step well.

CONCLUSION, LIMITATION, AND SUGGESTION

Conclusion

Based on the research that has been conducted, it can be concluded that the Quizizz-based picture and picture type cooperative learning model has a significant effect on the ability to master English vocabulary of elementary school students. Evidenced by the increase in the acquisition of scores that were previously far below the KKM, with the application of the Quizizz-based picture and picture type cooperative learning model increased to above the KKM.

Limitation

The duration of the research did not take place as the researcher had hoped. There are many factors that disrupt the research process. So that researchers need to do time management as much as possible so that the research is still carried out properly.

Suggestion

As a suggestion for further research, in the future researchers can use as many images as possible to be used as learning media. So that the Quizizz-based cooperative learning model can take place more optimally.

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